

STRATEGY DEVELOPMENT AND BRAND MANAGEMENT COMPANY

Shohboz Hamdambek o'g'li Ruzimatov

Tashkent State university
of economics Tashkent, Uzbekistan

Abstract: ArticleIn the article the questions of formation and implementation of enterprise brand management strategy, revealed the main stages of its formation, as well as the criteria for effective advertising communications. Also developed a complex scheme of forming a strategy development and brand management company.

Keywords: brand companies, advertising communication strategy.

A lot of different literature is devoted to the formation of a brand development and management strategy today.

Introduction. The conducted research has shown that in most of the works of domestic specialists, the strategy of brand development and management is not fully considered, and the strategies of brand development and management of foreign researchers often do not take into account the specificity of the Russian market. However, it is the issues of forming a strategy for developing and managing a brand that are most relevant today for most domestic enterprises engaged in the market of mass-demand goods and do not yet have their own brand. Which determined the need for further consideration of this issue.

The success of the brand with the consumer is based on an effective strategy of brand development and management, which should be understood as a consistent set of interactions between the enterprise and consumers, their forms and methods, through which

the main goal of the enterprise in the field of branding is achieved.

The basis of the company's brand development and management strategy is the product (or service), the material component of the brand, which is offered for sale to the consumer and must meet its functional needs for this product. The quality of the product plays a primary role in creating an individual image of the future brand, which is strengthened in the minds of the consumer, and in the future, a trusting long-term relationship.

Today, 60% of buyers consistently associate a trademark with a certain quality of the product, another 30% with the quality and its belonging to this particular enterprise, only the remaining 10% do not pay attention to the trademark when choosing goods or services. Therefore, more than 80% of all products produced in the world are marked with trademarks.

Due to the fact that most consumers associate brands primarily with high quality, the customer's disappointment at the first purchase from the purchase of a low-quality product or service casts doubt on the possibility of further forming a strategy for developing and managing the company's brand.

The correctness of this statement is confirmed by the opinions of various experts in the field of branding and marketing. Thus, a well-known marketing specialist Peter Doyle, considering the elements of a brand development and management strategy, believes that it is possible to create an enterprise brand by consistently passing three stages: – Creating a high – quality product that meets the needs of customers; - Conducting an effective Presentation; - Expanding the brand base, complementing it with other products and services.

In the future, P. Doyle suggests constantly initiating purchases from the consumer by means of advertising communications (exhibitions, direct advertising,

PR, presentations, lotteries, etc.) and conducting other events to strengthen the created brand and increase its value within the framework of the developed strategy.

Highlighting the creation of a quality product as the first stage of the company's brand development and management strategy and attaching special importance to this, P. Doyle, unfortunately, does not consider the entire chain of formation of this strategy, but only indicates the key points, which in turn consist of separate independent elements that deserve detailed analysis.

As practice has shown, for the majority of domestic enterprises engaged in the market of mass-demand goods, the availability of high-quality goods is a necessary, but not sufficient condition for the successful formation of a strategy for the development and management of the company's brand. The reason for this is, first of all, strong competition in the same product group and a high level of quality of production of many consumer goods.

As a result of the research of the practical experience of various domestic enterprises, it was revealed that the formation of the strategy for the development and management of the company's brand can be represented in the form of a certain algorithmic structure consisting of the following elements: 1. Formation of the brand's business idea; 2. Market analysis: - segmentation; - assessment of the market capacity and its segments, market dynamics – - study of competitors; 3. Creation of a quality product or service; 4. Identification and individualization of the product; 5. Increase in sales volume in the territory of the future brand; 6. Advertising communications to the consumer; 7. Formation of the importance of the brand ideology in the enterprise; 8. Winning a loyal majority; 9. Strengthening the brand idea in the consumer's mind; 10. Consumers ' belief in brand values and equating

them with their own (sometimes universal) values. 11. Further long-term brand management.

It is important to note that one of the first stages of the formation of the proposed strategy for the development and management of the company's brand should not be the creation of a product, but the development and formalization of a business idea.

The main economic goal of any company that creates its own brand is to increase the competitiveness and market value of its own goods. The development of a business idea allows you to formulate clear goals of the enterprise, pursued in the formation of the brand: long-term and short-term plans, criteria for determining success, tactical and strategic aspects of entrepreneurial activity, etc.

The issue of developing business ideas is relevant today, and is of paramount importance for many enterprises in the consumer market of goods and services. Studies of the practical experience of domestic enterprises have shown that in most cases, enterprises neglect the development of a business idea,

and begin their activities with the production of a certain product. The proposed element of the strategy for the development and management of the company's brand is the development of a business idea, which allows you to more effectively solve the issues of strategic planning for the development of the brand, and often the development of the company itself.

The development of a business idea also involves the definition of values, the orientation of which for the brand will be the basis of customer preference. Preliminary market analysis helps to clarify the formed business idea, determine the key positions of the brand in the market, assess its capacity, dynamics and level of

competition of the product niche. It is necessary to develop the position of the future brand in the market, conduct consumer segmentation.

Market research, its dynamics, consumer behavior and competitive analysis should be carried out by highly qualified specialists in close cooperation with the company's personnel. The effectiveness of such interaction depends on the degree of involvement of the company's employees in the process of researching the future position of the company's brand. The forms of participation of the staff can be different from filling out questionnaires to a personal conversation.

Based on the obtained data, a product is developed and created that meets the following main criteria: – The product must be in demand (relevant); - Have high quality; - Designed to meet the needs of a certain target audience of consumers; - Legally competent in the territory of distribution.

In the case when the company already has a finished product, it is necessary to modify it to meet the specified conditions.

The product offered to the market as part of the company's brand development and management strategy should be recognizable and easily identified by the consumer. These tasks are designed to solve the external attributes of the brand: packaging, corporate identity, color scheme, original way of selling the product, etc.

Classic examples of brand color identification are McDonald's (yellow and red), Coca-Cola (red), and IBM (blue). Product identification should be understood primarily as the development of the brand's corporate identity, its external presentation to the consumer, as well as all advertising materials. The integrated integration of identification and individualization, which require simultaneous development, helps to increase the effectiveness of brand recognition. Brand

individualization development of an image that needs to be formed in the consumer's mind with the help of identification tools.

The role of the availability of the product-brand at the points of sale (availability) is relevant for the formation of the strategy for the development and management of the company's brand. The analysis of the literature sources devoted to the formation of the strategy for the development and management of the company's brand has shown that this issue is practically not addressed in the branding literature. It is known that an excellent product in the market of mass demand goods, available only in 20% of retail outlets, is unlikely to win over a weaker one, available in 100% of retail outlets. Any brand is designed to bring its owner super-benefits in relation to other competitive products, and not defeat. Therefore, this issue is also an important element in the formation of the company's brand development and management strategy.

Increasing the sales volume in the territory of the future brand is one of the key aspects of the formation of the company's brand development and management strategy. The effectiveness of sales growth is dependent on advertising communications initiated by the company at the same time when the company is making efforts to expand the territory of distribution of its own goods.

The main criteria for effective advertising communications are: - Compliance with the general idea of the brand; - Clear formation of brand advantages in the consumer's mind; - Focus on the target audience of potential buyers; - Ease of perception for the target audience; - Compliance with the brand individualization strategy; - Achieving consumer awareness of the brand.

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